

Biofabrication

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Mechanical memory based biofabrication of hierarchical elastic cardiac tissue

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Abstract

Mimicking the multilayered, anisotropic, elastic structure of cardiac tissues for controlled guidance of 3D cellular orientation is essential in designing bionic scaffolds for cardiac tissue biofabrication. Here, a hierarchically organized, anisotropic, wavy and conductive polycaprolactone/Au scaffold was created in a facile fashion based on mechanical memory during fabrication. The bionic 3D scaffold shows good biocompatibility, excellent biomimetic mechanical properties that guide myoblast alignment, support the hyperelastic behavior observed in native cardiac muscle tissue, and promote myotube maturation, which holds potential for cardiac muscle engineering and the establishment of an *in vitro* culture platform for drug screening.

1. Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) have become a critical international health issue, and myocardial infarction (MI) accounts for the majority of CVD cases. Tissue engineering has been demonstrated to address potential approaches for cardiac tissue regeneration [1–6], where many types of biomaterial structures have been investigated for cardiac tissue engineering [7–11]. A promising approach is the creation of ‘cardiac patches’ [12–14], aiming to replicate the biological and mechanical properties of the heart, particularly by resembling the extracellular matrix (ECM) environment to promote cell maturation, and support organ function [15–18]. Heart muscles are richly vascularized, dense, quasi-lamellar tissues in which multiple layers of the ECM and highly oriented cells pack together [19–21]. Therefore, to effectively simulate complex 3D anisotropic structures and replicate the biological function of natural cardiac tissue, the development of scaffold structures that can guide the orientation of cells and tissues in a 3D environment is the key to promote the cardiac tissue engineering.

Different approaches for generating engineered scaffolds for 3D cardiac tissues have been explored

[22–25]. Feiner *et al* developed a heart patch that was able to bind heart cells together with separate electronics and composite scaffolds; this patch can record cell electrical activity and provide electrical stimulation (ES) on demand and synchronize cell contraction [26]. Mehrotra *et al* created directionally anisotropic cardiac patches by extrusion printing a blended bioink and demonstrated the alignment of neonatal rat cardiomyocytes with sarcomere formation and synchronous beating [3]. Compared to anisotropic constructs, customized designs can bear deformations in various directions. Cui *et al* created a physiologically adaptable wavy cardiac patch with both anisotropic and auxiliary properties by stereolithography printing a photocrosslinkable hydrogel blend. The *in vitro* culture incorporating mechanical stimulation improved cardiomyocyte maturation, and the *in vivo* study confirmed high levels of cell engraftment and vascularization of the patches [27]. Wang *et al* introduced the use of an injectable shape-memory cardiac patch. The conductive elastin–gelatin–carbon patch seeded with cardiomyocytes improved tissue repair in rat and porcine models of MI [28]. Shevach *et al* incorporated gold-nanoparticles into macroporous electrospun

polycaprolactone (PCL)–gelatin scaffolds to increase scaffold conductivity, and consequently electrical transfer between cells. This research showed that gold coating increases cardiac sarcomeric actinin expression, and cells also exhibit higher contraction rates than those on uncoated scaffolds [29]. Zhang *et al* proposed an anisotropic and conductive scaffold in combination with ES that mediated electrical signal transmittance and promoted myotube maturation [30]. Zhao *et al* built a scalable tissue-cultivation platform that enables the creation of electrophysiologically distinct atrial and ventricular tissues [31]. However, there are still few reports on developing a straightforward biofabrication method that incorporates multiscale anisotropic structural features to provide a biomimetic 3D mechanical environment.

Here, we propose a facile mechanical memory-based method to engineer a hierarchically organized, anisotropic, wavy and conductive PCL/Au scaffold, to guide myoblast alignment and promote the maturation of myoblasts into myotubes. To mimic the complex interwoven structure of natural cardiac tissue and control the arrangement and elongation of cells, we used melt electrowriting (MEW) to print PCL microfibers with a spacing of 200 μm, on which the aligned PCL submicron fibers were

solution electrospun (SES) via mechanical stretching (figure 1(a)). A wavy structure of the MEW fibers was generated after the microfibers had returned to their relaxed state (figure 1(b)), which was caused by the release of the deformation energy introduced by the prestress. Specifically, the transition from mechanical stretching to mechanical relaxation of the microfibers provides mechanical memory to realize mechanical programming of the scaffolds. Thus, microscale wavy topographical cues can be obtained simultaneously. Then, the micro/nanofiber scaffolds were successfully rendered conductive by sputter coating them with gold. The morphology and mechanical performance of scaffolds were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), respectively. The coating of Au was analyzed by energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). The biocompatibility and cytotoxicity were assessed by cell counting kit-8 (CCK-8) proliferation assay, as well as live–dead assay. The effect of topological cues on the directional differentiation and myotube maturation of H9c2 cells was evaluated by immunofluorescence staining and fluorescence imaging. Additionally, the impact of ES on these processes was also assessed. The H9c2 cells is a valuable *in vitro* model that have been widely used for

Figure 2. Preparation and characterization of 3D scaffolds with nano- and micro-structures. (a)–(d) SEM images of melt MEW (a) and SES (b)–(d) PCL fibers. (e)–(h) SEM image of 3D-scaffold MEW fibers and SES PCL mesh with random and aligned SES fiber distributions. (i) Fiber diameter and (j) alignment of the SES fibers underneath the MEW fibers. (k) Amplitude of MEW fiber waves and (l) EDX analysis of gold-coated conductive 3D scaffolds.

studying various aspects of cardiomyocyte physiology and pathophysiology, which preserve some features of cardiomyocytes in aspects of electrophysiology and hormonal regulation [32–34].

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Characterization of 3D scaffolds with nano- and micro-structures

To study the synergistic effect of micro/nano-scale topographic cues and electroactive signals on myotube formation, 3D hierarchically organized wavy fibrous scaffolds with aligned submicron fibers on the top of patterned microgrooves were fabricated. The morphology of the micro/nanoscale fibers was examined via SEM imaging. Figure 2(a) shows the SEM image of the MEW fibers with a spacing of 200 μm and mean diameter of ~20 μm, which are comparable to the fiber diameters of myocardial muscle [35]. Figures 2(b)–(d) shows the SEM images of the SES fibers at different drum rotation speeds,

where it is found that fiber alignment was improved at high rotational speeds (above 1500 rpm).

To introduce nanoscale topological cues and provide a mechanically load-bearing component to the scaffolds, a $10.0 \pm 3.6 \mu\text{m}$ thick PCL SES sub-micron fibrous mesh was electrospun on top of the prepared MEW fibers. Here, we hypothesize that the MEW fibers can be manipulated to adopt a wavy conformation after the tension introduced during the stretching of aligned SES fibers is released. The tension stored by the stretched SES fibers as they align on the rotating collector drum is released when the scaffold is taken off from the drum. The effect of increasing rotation speed on the SES fiber orientation can be observed in figures 2(i)–(k). At 0 rpm, random SES fibers were produced, and the MEW fibers maintained their straight fiber orientation. The wavy morphology was observed when rpm reached to 1500 rpm and became increasingly defined with increasing rotation speed, resulting in wavy structures with the highest amplitude at a 2500 rpm rotation

speed. Herein, the amplitude refers to the height of the wavy fiber from the midline to the highest point (or to the lowest point), as shown in figure 1(a).

Concerning printing efficiency, wavy scaffolds can also be produced by MEW itself using G-code or at a printing speed less than the critical translation speed [36]. However, this requires a slower fabrication process, and often needs a conductive printing surface, both of which have been overcome in the biofabrication method proposed in this work. For example, our previous research [37] showed that sinusoidal MEW fibers can be obtained at a lower print speed of 500 mm min^{-1} . The method proposed in this work is to prepare straight fibers at a speed of 2000 mm min^{-1} and then use mechanical stretching to directly obtain wavy fibers. In other words, when preparing wavy fiber samples with the same yield, the MEW printing efficiency can be increased by 4 times through the preparation method proposed in this paper. For example, the preparation of a wavy fiber sample of the same size as A4 paper ($210 \text{ mm} \times 297 \text{ mm}$) with a spacing of $200 \mu\text{m}$ takes only 155.88 min using the method described in this paper, which can be cut out approximately 124 740 $\text{O}6 \text{ mm}$ samples fit for 96-well plates.

As shown in figure 2(i), the random SES fibers exhibited the highest fiber diameter, approximately $1.5 \mu\text{m}$, and with increasing rotation speed the fiber diameter decreased to 757 nm . The degree of fiber alignment on the random scaffold varied widely, while the degree of alignment with the aligned scaffolds had a lower standard deviation (figure 2(j)). To characterize the wavy shape of the MEW fibers, the amplitude of the fiber waves was quantified (figure 2(k)). The mean wave amplitude of the aligned-1500 rpm scaffold was $21.9 \pm 9.1 \mu\text{m}$, whereas the mean wave amplitudes of the aligned-2000 rpm and aligned-2500 rpm scaffolds were $27.1 \pm 10.7 \mu\text{m}$ and $27.7 \pm 5.0 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. We observed that well-defined waves were more consistently produced throughout the whole scaffold at 2500 rpm. For this reason, this speed was chosen to produce scaffolds for mechanical testing and cell studies. Hereafter, the scaffolds with aligned SES fibers and a wavy MEW mesh morphology are referred to as wavy scaffolds, and the random SES fiber mesh scaffold with a straight MEW fiber structure is referred to as the straight scaffold.

A 50 nm gold layer coated on top of SES fibers had a comparable conductivity (1.2 S m^{-1}) to that of native muscle tissue (0.58 S m^{-1}) [38]. To confirm the presence and uniformity of the 50 nm gold-coated layer on the wavy scaffolds, EDS mapping was carried out. As shown in figure 2(l), the gold nanoparticles were evenly distributed on the surface of the PCL scaffold, while the mass fraction of Au was 32.5%, similar to the results of Zhang *et al* (37.9%) [21].

2.2. Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of the straight, wavy and gold coated wavy scaffolds were first assessed via uniaxial tensile testing in the longitudinal direction, where the direction of the applied strain was parallel to the fiber orientation. In order to eliminate the influence of manufacturing errors on the mechanical properties of the scaffold, the experimental results were further verified by simulation calculation. Additionally, the simulation results allow for a more intuitive analysis of the scaffold's fracture behavior and stress distribution during the force process, which helps us better understand the biomechanical interaction between the scaffold and cells. The stress-strain curves obtained by uniaxial mechanical testing and finite element analysis (FEA) simulations are shown in figures 3(a) and (b). By comparing the simulation results with the experimental results, it can be observed that they not only exhibit similar slopes in the elastic stages, but also demonstrate a consistent trend in the yield and fracture stages. Both results indicated that the straight scaffolds gradually entered the yield stage at a strain of 20% (figure 3(a)) and the wavy scaffolds entered the yield stage at a strain of 30% (figure 3(b)). When the strain reached 40%, the wavy scaffold was in the fracture stage (figure 3(b)), which is consistent with the simulation results in figure 3(f). The physiological stretching deformation of the human heart can reach 10% at the early diastole and 15%–22% at the end of diastole [7], which indicates that the wavy scaffold designed can extend along the long axis to $\sim 30\%$ before undergoing irrecoverable deformation, compared to $\sim 20\%$ for the straight scaffolds, and up to 40% of the strain capacity can meet the need of higher strain of cardiac tissue. It is worth noting that the deviations between different samples are inevitable (figure 3(c)). The reason is that the submicron SES fibers of the designed scaffolds played a main role in the process of force and the mechanical performance of submicron SES fibers is highly dependent on the overall uniformity and reliability of the nanofibrous mats generated by electrospinning. However, these properties are difficult to guarantee due to the nature of the electrospinning process. Specifically, it is difficult to control the position, crystallinity, and density of nanofibers during deposition and collection owing to the instability and whipping motion of the electrospinning jet [39]. However, compared with the existing literatures on electrospun PCL fibers, the deviations in this paper are within the acceptable range [40–42].

In addition, the Young's modulus was determined according to the linear stage of the stress-strain curves, as shown in figure 3(d). Taking the straight scaffold as an example, the deviation between the experimental and simulation results is only 2.3 MPa,

indicating that the results of the mechanical property characterization are reliable. Wang *et al* demonstrated that the high-energy gold sputtering process had only a small effect on the PCL substrate, leaving the original properties of PCL, namely mechanical properties, biocompatibility and biodegradability, intact [28]. According to the experimental results shown in figure 3(d), the wavy structures tended to have a lower Young's modulus (~ 28 MPa for the wavy scaffold and ~ 24 MPa for the Au-wavy scaffold) than did the straight scaffolds with the random fiber mesh (~ 31 MPa). These values are higher than those of the PCL scaffold (16–18 MPa) [43] and PLA–PCL-copolymer scaffold (~ 18 MPa) [44], indicating that the SES fibers on the top of the MEW mesh greatly improve the mechanical load-bearing capacity of the 3D scaffold. Advantages of using a stiffer material *in vivo* include its positive effects on the reduction in the infarct area and the remodeling of left ventricle under the decreased stress in the heart wall [45]. The stress contours of the straight- and wavy scaffolds indicated that the submicron SES fibers played a main role (figures 3(e) and (f)). Importantly, compared to figures 3(e) and (f), the stress distribution on the wavy scaffold was more uniform than that on the straight scaffold during tensile deformation, which indicates that the biomechanical stimulation of the cell by the scaffold can be more effectively regulated by the wavy fiber design.

Under *in vivo* circumstances, cardiac patches need to withstand cyclic stretches for a long time period under changing frequencies, such as the human heartbeat, ranging from 60–150 beats per minute. Also, the viscoelastic behavior of biomaterial scaffolds is known to affect cell behavior. To assess the viscoelastic properties of the prepared scaffolds, DMA was performed. To reflect the physiological conditions, the selected testing parameters included strains of 10%, 15%, and 20%, with various amplitudes of sinusoidal displacement and frequencies ranging from 1 to 3 Hz, equivalent to 60–180 contractions per minute. As shown in figures 3(g)–(i), the complex modulus of the different scaffolds was illustrated as a function of the number of stretching cycles at 1, 2 and 3 Hz. Generally, all scaffold types showed similar tendencies throughout the cycles at all strains. A higher complex modulus starts at the beginning of the strain at 1 Hz, followed by a small drop and then a slowly continuous decrease in the complex modulus. Among the three scaffolds tested, the straight scaffold had the lowest complex modulus according to the DMA test, while the gold-coated wavy scaffold had the highest complex modulus (10–8 MPa at 10% strain) compared to that of the straight or wavy fibers. This increase can be attributed to the high ductility of the gold coating, as shown by Wang *et al* [46]. A higher complex modulus indicates a stiffer, less viscoelastic material, while a lower complex modulus

means a softer, more elastic material. Several hydrogel materials intended for cardiac patches with complex modulus in the range of 0.02–0.1 MPa have been reported [47], whereas the complex modulus of published polymer blend cardiac patches can reach as high as 20–100 MPa [48]. Therefore, the complex modulus obtained in our scaffold is conducive to the extensive range of mechanical properties for cardiac patch application.

The frequency and strain range of cyclic stretches to which the scaffold is subjected are also critical for cellular growth. In previous studies, the viability and functional maturation of cardiac tissue were shown to be significantly enhanced by cyclical stretching at a frequency of 1.25 Hz [49]. Moreover, appropriate cyclical stretching can also influence the expression of enzyme activity and the conduction of ion signals. For example, within a cycle frequency range of 1–4 Hz and a stretch amplitude of 3%–15%, there is a significant elevation in steady-state Nox2-dependent ROS production in cardiomyocytes and effective adjustment of Ca^{2+} signaling [50]. Additionally, the contraction frequency of human cardiomyocytes within the first 3 months after birth was confirmed to be 1.7–2.5 Hz [51]. Clearly, our scaffolds exhibited excellent tensile properties in the abovementioned cycle frequency and tensile strain ranges, indicating that the developed wavy scaffold has the potential to provide effective cycle stress stimulation for the growth and maturation of myocardial tissue.

2.3. Cell proliferation and biocompatibility of H9c2 cells

To assess the effects of nanoscale and microscale topographical cues, ES and their combination on cell proliferation and biocompatibility, H9c2 cells were seeded onto straight, wavy and Au-coated wavy scaffolds. Two experimental groups were included (ES-Wavy and Au-ES-Wavy), in which the cells received ES for 1 h per day starting from day 2 (100 Hz frequency, 2 V voltage) for 5 d. The optimal parameter of ES chosen for this study was based on the previous literature, H9c2 can differentiate into skeletal and cardiac myocytes [32]. The existing researches show that high stimulation frequency (1–25 kHz) can be used for stimulating cardiac tissue to treat disease and trigger action potentials [52, 53], and skeletal muscle receives electrical signals from the nervous system, which contains several oscillatory bands covering frequencies from 0.05 Hz to 500 Hz [54], and the optimal electrical field usually ranges from 0.1 to 10 V cm^{-1} [55]. Tissue culture plates (TCPs) without gold coating or ES were included as a standard cell culture control group.

To further test the biocompatibility of the prepared scaffolds and the effect of ES on cell viability, live–dead staining was performed on day 12 of culture (figures 4(a)–(f)). Live cells were stained with calcein AM (green) fluorescent stain and dead cells were

stained with propidium iodide (red) fluorescent stain. No obvious dead cells were observed on the uncoated wavy and wavy-ES scaffolds while some dead cells can be observed in other groups, which indicates that the ES has almost no effect on cell viability. Overall, most cells on each group of scaffolds were alive. The above results are consistent with the previous research showing that H9c2 cells can proliferate and differentiate on PCL scaffolds [56], gold-coated PCL-scaffolds [38, 57] and under ES [58].

During the 11 d of culture, cell proliferation was monitored by a CCK-8 assay, as shown in figure 4(g). Cell proliferation on the 3D straight, ES-wavy and Au-ES-wavy scaffolds followed a similar trend to that on 2D TCP, but with a greater proliferation index. Notably, the wavy and gold-coated wavy scaffolds exhibited the highest proliferation indices on days 5 and 7, with the gold-coated wavy scaffolds showing a proliferation index nearly 3.18 times greater than that of TCP on day 7. This suggests that the wavy topology design significantly promotes cell proliferation due to its greater surface area from larger local surface curvature, which can provide more adhesion sites for cells and tend to increase surface cell density due to the deposition of cells on concave regions of the substrate reduces the local surface area, which has been demonstrated in previous studies [59–61]. The good growth of cells on the wavy scaffolds was further confirmed, as shown in figures 4(b) and (e). Overall, all the designed scaffolds provided a suitable environment for hosting H9c2 cells, and the ES did not affect cell viability.

In addition, the proliferation behavior of cells on different scaffolds was similar. The proliferation index was higher on the fifth and seventh days, because after the cells were implanted on the scaffold, between 48 and 150 h post seeding, the H9c2 cells enter the doubling time. During this phase, the cell proliferation rate was the fastest and the number of cells increased sharply. The similar research result was obtained in [62]. When the cell density reaches a certain level, cell proliferation slows down and eventually tends to stop. This explains the significant increase in the cell proliferation index on the fifth day and the decrease in proliferation speed on the seventh day. The wavy scaffold has a higher surface area to support a large number of attached cells, resulting in a higher proliferation index on days 5 and 7. Similar phenomena can be observed in previous work [38, 63].

2.4. Effect of topological cues and ES on H9c2 myotube formation

In order to study the effect of different topographical cues on myotube formation, H9c2 cells were seeded onto straight, wavy and Au-coated wavy scaffolds. After 8 d of culture in differentiation medium, H9c2 cells were stained red for myosin heavy chain (MHC), a protein marker for myotube formation, which was also reported in detail in our previous work

Figure 4. Cell viability and proliferation of H9c2 cells. (a)–(f) Cell viability on 3D-scaffolds with and without gold coating and electrical stimulation (scale bar: 400 μm). (g) Cell proliferation index on the various scaffolds on day 1, 3, 5 and 7.

[30]. Generally, cells were present at high densities under all conditions. In the TCP control group, the cells formed myotubes in various directions. On the straight scaffold, the myotubes following the alignment of the structure. Under all wavy scaffold conditions, the myotubes aligned with the underlying SES fibers and followed the waves of the MEW fibers. This finding agrees with the literature that the introduction of microgrooves has a significant impact on the directional growth of myotubes [64].

To quantify the effect of topographical cues on myotube formation, myotube length was measured on whole-scaffold stitched images (shown in figure 5) to compare the difference among different culture conditions (figures 6(a)–(f)), and the fusion ratio and maturation index were calculated. The fusion ratio was defined as the number of myotubes with 2 nuclei divided by the total number of myotubes measured, and the maturation index was the number of myotubes with 5 or more nuclei divided by the number of myotubes with 2 or more nuclei, as shown in figures 6(g)–(i). Interestingly, the myotube lengths in the straight ($468 \pm 257 \mu\text{m}$), wavy ($480 \pm 283 \mu\text{m}$) and Au-wavy groups ($522 \pm 404 \mu\text{m}$) were significantly greater than those in the TCP group

($166 \pm 87.1 \mu\text{m}$), where the Au-wavy scaffold had the longest myotube of $2481 \mu\text{m}$. Moreover, the length of the myotubes in the wavy group was greater than that in the straight group, which indicates that when the microgrooves are parallel to the direction of the SES fibers, the nanoscale fibers can not only guide the directional arrangement of myoblasts, but also promote the fusion of myoblasts into longer myotubes along the longitudinal extension direction of the microgrooves.

Although the ES did not further improve myotube length (figure 6(g)), it greatly enhanced the fusion of myoblasts to initiate myotube formation from 6.32% to 9.36% (figure 6(h)). While the maturation index for the TCP was approximately 25%, where most myotubes contained 3 or 4 nuclei, all scaffold groups demonstrated maturation index consistently exceeded 75%, reaching 97% and 92% in the wavy and ES-wavy groups, respectively (figure 6(i)). Previously, it was shown that introducing conductivity to scaffolds in the form of gold nanoparticles [38] or blending with a conductive polymer [65] increases myotube maturation. These results showed that nano- and micro-topographic signals not only promote the formation and directional extension

Figure 5. Myotube formation immunofluorescent stitched images of whole TCP well and scaffolds (scale bar = 2 mm).

of myotubes, but also effectively promote myotube maturation.

In summary, hierarchical topographic guidance combined with bioelectrical signaling plays a synergistic role in the differentiation of myoblasts. The aligned SES fibers can induce directional growth of cells, while together with ES, wavy MEW microgrooves effectively promoted the fusion and maturation of myotubes.

3. Methods

3.1. Materials and fabrication of 3D scaffolds with nano- and micro-structures

PCL pellets (Mn 45 000, Sigma-Aldrich) were used as raw material without any modification. 3D hierarchical wavy conductive fibers were fabricated via a multistep preparation process, consisting of melt-electrowritten PCL fibers and PCL nanofibrous

Figure 6. Effect of topographical and electrical cues on H9c2 cell myotube formation and elongation: (a)–(f) immunofluorescence images of H9c2 cells cultured on TCP or 3D PCL scaffolds with and without gold coating and electrical stimulation (scale bar: 400 μm). (g) Average myotube length (h) fusion ratio and (i) maturation index. (Kruskal–Wallis test, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.005$, *** $p < 0.0005$ **** $p < 0.00001$).

mesh. Briefly, a commercial melt electrowriting (MEW) machine was used to prepare microfibers with 200 μm spacing. PCL was melted at 75 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h before printing through a stainless-steel needle (24 G). A collector distance of 4 mm was used for all the samples, and the voltage, pressure and flow rate were set to 3.5 kV, 0.15 bar and 2000 mm min^{-1} , respectively. The spacing between the microgrooves was achieved by creating G-codes using standard 3D printing software. Then, PCL SES fibrous meshes were fabricated on top of the MEW fibers by using an electrospinner with a rotating drum collector. A 12% (w/v) PCL spinning solution was prepared by dissolving PCL pellets (Mn 80 000, Sigma-Aldrich) in a solvent mixture of chloroform/ethanol (4:1, v/v) and stirring overnight at room temperature (RT) to obtain a homogeneous solution. The homogenous solution was then loaded in a 5 ml plastic syringe with a 20 G needle. Electrospinning was then carried out at a constant pumping rate of 1 ml h^{-1} with a high voltage and distance of 18 kV and 15 cm respectively.

With the other parameters kept constant as above, a series of rotating speeds, including 1500, 2000 or 2500 rpm were adopted to obtain aligned SES fibers, while for random SES fibers a fixed drum (0 rpm) was used. Afterwards, the obtained SES fibers were air-dried, frozen and then vacuum freeze-dried for two days to remove residual solvents.

To prepare gold-coated scaffolds, a 50 nm gold nanolayer was distributed on the surface of the scaffolds to cover the MEW fibers and SES fibers by using a sputter coater. In previous studies [66], we demonstrated that coating a nanolayer of gold on the surface of PCL endows the PCL scaffold with high electrical conductivity. Gold particles have remarkable mechanical properties and long-term stability in water and are firmly bonded to the PCL by noncovalent bonding or van der Waals forces [67–69]. Therefore, the obtained Au-PCL scaffold can not only maintain the original good characteristics of PCL after sputtering but also provide a highly conductive interface that could affect cell electroactive activities.

3.2. Characterization

The fiber morphology of the prepared scaffolds was measured by SEM. The diameter and fiber orientation of the SES submicron fibers and the fiber diameter of the MEW microfibers were determined via ImageJ software analysis. The elemental composition of the scaffolds was analyzed by EDS and SEM.

Tensile stress measurements were completed both in long axial directions ($n = 4$ replicates per condition) at a constant strain rate of 0.1 mm s^{-1} . The test samples were placed in tensile grips with the dimensions of 5 mm length (L_0) and 10 mm width (W_0), where the direction of alignment and MEW fiber orientation were parallel to the length of the scaffolds. The scaffold thickness (H) was measured based on SEM images with ImageJ, yielding an estimated thickness of $10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. Tensile stress–strain curves were obtained based on the force–displacement curves, where the cross-section area was determined by the thickness and width of the printed scaffolds. The elastic modulus (E) was calculated according to the first linear stage of the stress–strain curves. The stress is therefore $\sigma = F/A$, $A = ((W_0 * H) + (W_0/0.2) * N * \varnothing)$, where N is the number of layers (10), \varnothing is the fiber diameter (0.021 mm) and 0.2 mm is the fiber spacing. The strain (ε) was calculated as $\varepsilon = \Delta L/L_0$, where ΔL is the length deformation.

In addition, the viscoelastic behavior of the prepared scaffolds ($n = 3$ replicates per condition) was evaluated by DMA. The samples were mounted in grips and first stretched at half of the total strain, which was 5%, 7.5% and 10%. A sinusoidal displacement with dynamic amplitudes of 5%, 7.5% and 10% strain was then applied, amounting to total strains of 10%, 15% and 20%, respectively. The different frequencies of displacement applied, including 1, 2 and 3 Hz, were used to test the complex modulus, which was determined by the resulting force (stress) generated during sinusoidal dynamic stretching.

3.3. Finite element analysis simulation

To ascertain the validity of the experiments and exclude potential experimental errors, FEA was carried out using Ansys Workbench (version 19.0, ANSYS Inc) to elucidate the obtained experimental outcomes. The scaffolds were constructed with the same geometric characteristics as the actual printed ones, in which, the wavy fiber is considered to be an ideal uniform wavy structure composed of centrally symmetric units similar to a sinusoidal function, with the amplitude consistent with that described in section 2.1. In the modeling process, a model of the whole wavy fibers was first established and then the wavy fibers were meshed with a hexahedral mesh to complete the subsequent FEA. The material properties of the PCL were as follows: the elastic modulus of 340 MPa, Poisson's ratio of 0.3, and density of 1.145 g cm^{-3} [70]. For the plastic stage, we used the

multilinear isotropic hardening model to characterize the stress–strain relationship in the plastic stage, and the data refer to [71, 72]. The mesh type of the models is all hexahedron mesh (C3D8R). One side of the scaffold was set as a fixed constraint and the other was stretched in the direction parallel to the PCL microfibers. The elastic modulus can be computed by

$$E = \frac{RF/A}{\Delta L/L_0} \quad (1)$$

where RF is the reaction force in the z direction and A is the cross-sectional area perpendicular to the tensile direction. $\Delta L/L$ denotes the tensile strain, where ΔL and L_0 are the length change and the initial length of the scaffold in the tensile direction, respectively. Here, the parameters A and L_0 are consistent with those of the experimental samples described in section 3.2, and ΔL is set to 6 mm. It is worth noting that the elastic results obtained in our work are time-dependent, which is intended to simulate real experimental conditions. During the simulation, we made the strain rate consistent with the parameters set in the tensile experiments.

3.4. Cell harvesting, seeding and culture

The H9c2 cell line, derived from embryonic BDIX rat heart tissue, was obtained from Merck. This kind of cells is a permanent cardiac cell line derived from embryonic heart tissue and has been shown to exhibit many properties of skeletal muscle such as the ability to fuse into multinucleated myotubes [73]. These cells were maintained in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium, supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum and 1% penicillin/streptomycin (P/S). Scaffolds were prepared using a biopsy puncher with a diameter of $\varnothing 6 \text{ mm}$ and were then carefully placed in 96-well plates. Both sides of the 96 well plate were sterilized under a 254 nm UV lamp for 40 min before cell seeding. Next, H9c2 cells in a $10 \text{ }\mu\text{l}$ cell suspension were seeded onto the scaffolds at a density of 10 000 cells per well for the TCP control wells and 100 000 cells per well for the scaffolds. After 1 h of incubation in a cell incubator ($37 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 5% CO_2), an additional $90 \text{ }\mu\text{l}$ of growth medium was added to each well. The following day (day 1), fresh growth medium was added, and the cells were cultured for 2 d. On day 3, differentiation medium (DMEM supplemented with 1% FBS and 1% P/S) was added, and the cells were cultured for an additional 8 d. Both the growth and differentiation media were changed every 2 d. Starting from day 5, the cells were subjected to 1 h of daily ES for 5 consecutive days, after which the differentiation medium was replaced each day during this period.

3.5. Cell proliferation and viability

A CCK-8 was used to assess the viability and proliferation of H9c2 cells. In brief, the cells were incubated in CCK-8 reagent diluted in culture medium (1:10)

for 1.5 h. Then, the media was removed, and the absorbance at 450 nm was measured using a Victor Multilabel Reader. In total, five replicates were measured in the assay. The proliferation rate was defined as follows:

$$PR_x = \frac{Ab_x}{Ab_1} \quad (2)$$

where PR_x is the proliferation rate on day x , Ab_x and Ab_1 is the absorbance values measured from CCK8 assay on day x and day 1, respectively.

To evaluate the viability of H9c2 after 11 d of culture, respectively, a live–dead assay was carried out. The green (Calcein-AM) and red (propidium iodide) fluorescent reagents were diluted in culture medium and mixed together just before use. Calcein-AM labels live cells whereas propidium iodide stains the nuclei of dead cells. The cells were incubated in staining solution for 30 min and subsequently imaged using an Invitrogen EVOS FL Auto Cell Imaging System.

3.6. Immunostaining and fluorescence imaging

After 10 d of H9c2 culture for differentiation, the samples ($n = 3$) were fixed with 4% formaldehyde in PBS for 15 min and washed 3 times with PBS. Afterwards, the samples were then permeabilized in PBS supplemented with 0.2% (v/v) Triton X-100 for 15 min at RT. After blocking in 1% BSA in PBS for 45 min at RT, H9c2 cells were incubated with Mouse Anti-Fast Myosin Skeletal Heavy chain primary antibody. After washing 3 times with PBS, the appropriate secondary antibodies were used at a 1:1000 dilution in 1% BSA in PBS for 1 h at RT. The cells were washed again 3 times for 10 min, before being incubated with HOECHST 33 258 (ThermoFisher) 1:10 000 for 10 min to stain the nuclei. Finally, the stained cells were visualized under a fluorescence microscope.

The quantification of myotubes was performed on stitched images of the scaffolds and TCP wells, herein, the MHC-positive index was defined as the ratio of MHC-positive cells to the total number of cells. Among the MHC-positive cells, the percentage of fused cells containing 2 or more nuclei was defined as the fusion index. The maturation index was defined as the ratio of the number of fused cells with >5 nuclei to the number of fused cells containing 2 or more nuclei [74].

3.7. Image analysis

The myotube formation on the various scaffolds was quantified using the ImageJ plugin NeuronJ [75]. The analysis included assessing the number and length of myotubes, as well as determining the fusion ratio and maturation index based on MHC-stained fluorescence images. The fusion ratio represents the number of myotubes with 2 nuclei divided by the total myotube count, while the maturation index signifies

the number of myotubes containing 5 or more nuclei divided by the total myotube count.

3.8. ES

A homemade platform was prepared to assess the effect of ES on cell growth and maturation. Sterilized aluminum electrodes were positioned within a 96-well plate, and their connection to an oscilloscope generator or a sinusoidal waveform generator was established using copper tape. The direction of the electrode is consistent with the long axial direction of the wavy fibers, in order to explore whether the ES can further enhance the guidance and promotion function of fibers to cardiac tissue.

For the H9c2 cells, an alternating current with a voltage of 2 V and a frequency of 100 Hz was applied for 1 h per day over a period of 5 d. Throughout the stimulation process, the cells were incubated with 5% CO₂ at 37 °C.

3.9. Statistics

The data are presented as the mean ± standard deviation. Statistical significance was analyzed using Kruskal–Wallis test with Dunn’s test to correct for multiple comparisons, with values of * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, and **** $p < 0.0001$ indicating significant differences.

4. Conclusions

In summary, we developed a simple and efficient strategy to prepare a 3D conductive hierarchically organized wavy PCL-scaffold by the stepwise combination of MEW fibers and an aligned SES submicron fibrous mesh, and demonstrated the great potential of this approach for guiding and promoting the growth and maturation of engineered cardiac muscle. The combination of nano- and micro-topological cues and gold-coating provides distinct hierarchal structures and electrostimulation functions. H9c2 cells were seeded and cultured on these scaffolds, and the results demonstrated the good biocompatibility of these designed 3D scaffolds and their ability to guide myoblast alignment and enhance the formation of myotubes. Furthermore, the mechanical properties of the designed scaffolds were characterized by experiments and simulation calculations, which indicated that the straight scaffold had the highest tensile Young’s modulus, while the Au-wavy scaffold had a better complex modulus, and met the design requirements of cardiac patches. These results indicate that these scaffolds can induce cell alignment, elongation and functional maturation and can provide a suitable 3D environment for mechanical protection, which suggests that these conductive hierarchically organized wavy scaffolds have great potential application in cardiac tissue engineering.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

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Author contributions

Z L: writing original draft, methodology, and formal analysis; P K: investigation, methodology, and validation; A L F: methodology and validation; B N J: supervision and methodology; J V N: methodology and writing review; M C : conceptualization, methodology, supervision, writing review and funding acquisition.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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